

**DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL SPEECH IN ADOLESCENCE.
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Anottatsiya: Adolescents are interested in the history of the origin of words, their exact meaning and essence. In his speech, he tries to pronounce words not like a young child, but like an adult, the article discusses the role of a teacher as a role model for the acquisition of speech culture in a teenager.

Key words: Adolescence, behavior, cognition, creative activity, speech.

The development of speech during adolescence is due to the increase of vocabulary on the one hand, and on the other hand due to the understanding of the essence of things, events and phenomena in nature and society. It is from the period of adolescence that a person begins to understand that the development of speech recognition processes is determined. Teenagers are often taught the rules of using words in communication - "How to write correctly?" "What better way to say it?" Questions like "What to say?" are very interesting. During this period, a teenager begins to feel that, in addition to reflecting the environment, he can define a person's worldview with the help of language. Adolescents quickly pay attention to the mistakes in the speech of teachers, adults, parents, books, newspapers, radio and television announcers. This situation, on the one hand, teaches the teenager to control his speech, and on the other hand, he learns that adults can also violate the rules of speech, and it leads to the elimination of his existing mistakes. A teenager is very interested in the history of the origin of words, their exact meaning and essence. In his speech, he tries to pronounce words not like a young child, but like an adult. The quality of school education serves as the main factor in changing the direction of the development of adolescent cognitive processes. With the correct organization and implementation of educational processes at school, conditions are created for the correct development of adolescent speech. The effort to master speech is a need and aspiration of a teenager to engage in communication, knowledge and creative activities. And monologue speech changes from retelling a small part of the work, to preparing speeches and performances independently, to verbal reasoning, expressing opinions and justifying them. During adolescence, reading skills, written and monologue speech develop rapidly. From the 5th grade to the 9th grade, reading increases from the level of being accurate, fast and expressive to the level of being able to

tell from memory expressively and effectively. As a result of the development of written speech, teenagers can independently write an essay on a given creative topic. . It forces you to analyze your speech by repeatedly reading the thought you have written. Teenagers' speech is carried out in a state of full contemplation. Students in grades 5-6 can make a plan for oral and written text and follow it. When the student is writing, he often has to revise, change, complete, and re-develop his work several times. Adolescents begin to engage in more serious work, devoting less time to games and entertainment, and their cognitive processes begin to develop rapidly. Independent forms of training are pleasant for them. School education serves as the main factor in qualitatively changing the direction of the development of adolescent cognitive processes. Studying plays an important role in the life of teenagers. Compared to children of other eras, teenagers' successful learning of subjects, increased interest, depends on the teacher's ability to explain the educational material. On the basis of reading activities, the level of self-awareness of a teenager expands, his knowledge about other people and the world deepens. During this period, new motivations for studying appear. These motives have an impact on the character of the development of cognitive processes in connection with the adolescent's life plans, future profession and ideal. A new stage of mental development begins. Based on the needs of learning knowledge, a positive attitude towards academic subjects is gradually formed.

The effort to master speech is the need and desire of a teenager to engage in communication, knowledge and creative activities. Right from adolescence, children feel a special need to expand their life, scientific and artistic knowledge and try to do so. Educated students are respected among their peers. Knowledge brings a special joy to teenagers and develops their ability to think.

Children's acquisition of written speech is an important stage in the development of their speech. The student learns to understand written speech correctly, learns to express his thoughts in written speech and explain to others. Reading a book and especially expressing and explaining one's thoughts in writing is of great importance in mastering the grammatical structure of the language. The need to fully explain the idea during the written statement forces the student to pay attention not only to the content of what he writes, but also to how he writes.

In the development of cognitive processes, speech is a powerful tool, both oral and written. With the correct organization and implementation of educational processes at school, favorable conditions are created for the correct

development of adolescent speech. Mastering written speech helps to make oral speech, and especially monologue speech, more accurate and comprehensive. The fact that the student constantly practices speaking the task to himself during the preparation of the task given at school has a great impact on the growth of the student's speech. This is when the student is preparing lessons not only does he read the lessons from the book, but usually he closes the book and tells it to himself or to a partner next to him. In such cases, the student should make the lesson he/she is preparing especially comprehensible, following the grammar rules correctly tries to tell orally:

-The learner exercises his articulatory apparatus by repeating it out loud, literally or in his own words, controlling the accuracy of his speech, while at the same time also controls the correctness and consistency of the acquired knowledge.

In conclusion, the teacher's speech plays a big role in the growth of the student's speech, because the teacher's speech is a model speech for students. Therefore, every teacher should strive to improve the speech of students, and he should constantly and tirelessly seek to improve his own speech.

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